

Alkali Metal Complexes : Complexes of Di-Lithium-, Di-Sodium-, and Di-Potassium-EDTA with Oxalic and Malonic Acids

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The hydrated di-sodium- and di-potassium-EDTA (M_2H_2EDTA , where $M=Na$ or K) derivatives lose water molecules at 190° and 125° respectively, which shows strong association. Infrared spectra show that these water molecules are coordinated. These water molecules have been replaced by oxalic and malonic acids and compounds of the general formula $M_2H_2EDTA.X$, where $M=Li, Na$ or K and $X=oxalic$ or malonic acid, have been synthesised in absolute alcohol.

The antisymmetric carboxylate stretching frequency between $1635-1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for di-sodium- and di-potassium-EDTA is diagnostic of coordinated carboxylate groups. Difference, Δ_ν , between symmetric and antisymmetric COO^- stretching frequencies of these compounds (which is $235-240\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is higher than for the ionized $-COO^-$ ($\Delta_\nu < 225\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

THE complexes formed between alkaline earth cations¹ and transition cations²⁻⁶ with ethylenediaminetetra acetic acid (EDTA), have been discussed in detail, and the use of the infrared technique for these systems has also been reviewed^{1,4}. All the previous investigators¹⁻⁶ have assumed that bonding for $EDTA-2M^+$ salts ($M^+=alkali\ cation$) is ionic, though their infrared data had been contradictory to their findings and explanations. Their work indicated that there was some interaction between the ligand and the alkali metals^{1,4} which had been supported by the stability constant values⁷.

The earlier workers have shown that bonding between transition cations²⁻⁶ and EDTA is mainly covalent, whereas the one with alkaline earth cations¹ is essentially ionic. They have used the infrared technique to determine whether the bonding is covalent or ionic. In this paper we report the use of this technique for a similar study of the $EDTA-M^+$ systems where $M^+=Li^+, Na^+, K^+$.

Experimental

Complexes of di-lithium salt of EDTA: The hydrated di-lithium salt of EDTA was heated for one hour at 156° . The anhydrous salt was treated with saturated ethanolic solution of oxalic acid or malonic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes with constant stirring. In the case of oxalic acid and Li_2H_2EDTA , the complex crystallised immediately after the addition of Li_2H_2EDTA , even in cold. In the case of malonic acid, the complex crystallises if the mixture is kept overnight after it was refluxed for 30 minutes with constant stirring. Then it was filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 80° .

Complexes of di-sodium salt of EDTA: The hydrated di-sodium salt of EDTA was heated in an oven for one hour at 190° to make it anhydrous. Then the complexes with oxalic acid or malonic acid were prepared similarly as mentioned in the case of Li_2H_2EDTA except that in case of oxalic acid, the complex comes out immediately after the addition of anhydrous Na_2H_2EDTA , i.e., shaking the mixture for 5 minutes, even in cold.

Complexes of di-potassium salt of EDTA: The hydrated di-potassium salt of EDTA was heated in an oven for one hour at 135° to make it anhydrous and the complexes with oxalic acid or malonic acids were then prepared as mentioned in the case of Li_2H_2EDTA .

Results and Discussion

The presence of water in all solid EDTA compounds, permits the assumption that water molecules are coordinated. For the hydrated complexes, $Na_2H_2EDTA.2H_2O$ and $K_2H_2EDTA.2H_2O$, a dehydration step begins above 120° and ends at 190° which involves the removal of firmly bonded water. This suggests that water is an essential component of the structure.

Di-sodium- and di-potassium-EDTA hydrates lose water at 190° and 120° respectively. Compared to the anhydrous compounds, the hydrated derivatives show an extra peak, both for sodium (1080 cm^{-1}) and potassium (810 cm^{-1}). This according to Nakamoto⁸ is due to the rocking mode of coordinated water.

The i.r. data shows that in EDTA, carboxyl group is not ionised as would be expected for a betaine structure. The frequency of the carboxyl band at 1697 cm^{-1} in the acid shows carboxyl groups to be quite normal and presumably hydrogen bonded.

The spectrum of the hydrated EDTA-2Na⁺ shows two bands at 1686 and 1637 cm^{-1} and two strong O-H stretching bands in the 3300 cm^{-1} region, out of which latter vanishes on heating the compound. The spectrum of the tetrasodium compound, showing a strong broad band at 1595 cm^{-1} , suggests the existence of differently bonded carboxyl groups in disodium salt.

The position of the carboxyl peak in the infrared spectra of EDTA complexes has been employed¹⁻⁴ as indication of the nature of M⁺-O bonding. The positions of the carboxyl peak maxima arising from the -COOM group in EDTA are shown in Table-1.

The strongest absorptions due to carboxylate group (COO⁻) is at $1600\text{-}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$; this frequency

bonding is not ionic, as presumed by earlier workers¹⁻⁴.

The tetrasodium- and tetrapotassium-EDTA with carboxylate frequencies at 1605 and 1595 cm^{-1} respectively, fall in the ionic category; but some association is still indicated, since their frequency is greater than that obtained for the Ba-chelate¹, as more strongly acidic Ba²⁺ forms weak bond. This conclusion is again supported by the work of Schwarzenbach and Ackermann⁷, who have reported a stability constant for the EDTA complex of sodium ion ($\log K = 1.66$).

By using the frequency difference between the asymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ group as the criterion for the degree of covalent character for the metal carboxylate bonds, an arbitrary designation has been made that the bonds are primarily covalent when the difference is 225 cm^{-1} or more. When the difference is less than 225 cm^{-1} , the bonding is primarily ionic.

An examination of alkali metal EDTA compounds shows that Li₂, Na₂- and K₂H₂EDTA with higher values ($235, 240$ and 235 cm^{-1}) than 225 cm^{-1} falls in the covalent category, Na₃HEDTA is borderline with 225 cm^{-1} , and Na₄- and K₄EDTA are ionic with lower values (195 cm^{-1}).

The degree of covalent character for the N-M⁺ bond is related to the absorption frequency due to

TABLE-1, FREQUENCY SEPARATION FOR THE MAJOR ANTISYMMETRICAL AND SYMMETRICAL VIBRATIONS OF THE COO⁻ GROUPS IN EDTA CHELATES.

Chelate	Antisymmetric frequency cm^{-1}	Symmetric frequency cm^{-1}	Frequency difference cm^{-1}
Li ₂ H ₂ Y.nH ₂ O	1635	1400	235
Na ₂ H ₂ Y.2H ₂ O	1630	1395	235
Na ₃ H ₂ Y	1635	1395	240
Na ₃ HY.5H ₂ O	1625	1400	225
Na ₄ Y	1605	1410	195
K ₂ H ₂ Y.2H ₂ O	1625	1395	230
K ₃ H ₂ Y	1630	1395	235
K ₄ Y	1595	1400	195

Y = Ethylenediamine tetra acetate.

has been used to indicate degree of covalency in the -COO⁻-M⁺ bond¹⁻⁴, for the asymmetric stretching frequency varies considerably as M is changed⁵. For H₄EDTA, and M₄⁺-EDTA, it appears around 1700 and $1600\text{-}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. If the covalency of O-M bond is increased, carboxylate resonance is partially blocked and the frequency⁶ is shifted higher, and its absorption can be taken as a measure of the covalent character of the M⁺-OOC bond. For the essentially covalently bonded Co(III)-EDTA⁸, the frequency is at 1645 cm^{-1} , but for the essentially ionic Cd(II) salts, it is around 1600 cm^{-1} . For Li₂H₂EDTA, Na₂H₂EDTA and K₂H₂EDTA, these frequencies appear at $1635, 1635$ and 1630 cm^{-1} respectively (Table-1), which indicates that M⁺-O

C-N group; the frequency increases as the bond becomes more covalent. For the transition metal-EDTA⁹ complexes, it appears⁹ at 1100 cm^{-1} . For the Na₃⁺-EDTA it appears at 1056 cm^{-1} , for the trisodium salt at 1125 cm^{-1} and 1055 cm^{-1} and for the tetrasodium compound at 1120 cm^{-1} , which may not be surprising when it is assumed that all these compounds show complexation. For K₂H₂EDTA and K₄EDTA, it appears at 1060 cm^{-1} and 1130 cm^{-1} . These values are comparable to those for covalently bonded cation salts.

It is suggested that water molecule occupies the fourth position around cation in the salt (Sketch-1). The two water molecules have been replaced by

TABLE-2

Compound	Colour	Decomposition Tem. (°C).	Found (%)				Calculated (%)			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
Li ₂ H ₂ Y.Oxal	White	210-215 d	36.20	4.30	7.31	-	36.55	4.06	7.11	-
Li ₂ H ₂ Y.Mal	White	228-230 d	38.50	4.81	7.15	-	38.24	4.41	6.86	-
Na ₂ H ₂ Y.Oxal	White	224-226 mcd	33.20	4.106	.92	11.05	33.80	3.76	6.57	10.80
Na ₂ H ₂ Y.Mal	White	218-220 mcd	34.98	4.57	6.64	10.78	35.5	4.10	6.36	10.45
K ₂ H ₂ Y.Oxal	White	220-222 m	30.80	3.46	5.92	16.71	31.44	3.49	6.11	17.03
K ₂ H ₂ Y.Mal	White	160 m	32.87	3.64	6.12	16.20	33.05	3.81	5.93	16.53

Y = Ethylenediamine tetra acetate ; Oxal = oxalic acid ; Mal = malonic acid.

oxalic or malonic acid (Table-2). The structural aspects of these compounds (M₂H₂EDTA. X, where M = Li, Na and K ; and X = oxalic acid or malonic acid) is shown in sketch II. These products have

Sketch-II

higher melting points than the stoichiometric mixtures of their components. None of these complexes shows the broad and characteristic zwitter ion absorption at 3000-2400 cm⁻¹ region, showing the absence of >NH⁺ bands.

Nakamoto⁸ has tabulated the carboxylic acid frequencies of M-EDTA compounds into three categories : un-ionised COOH, coordinated COO...

and free COO⁻, but has not classified the Na salt (1637 cm⁻¹) in the coordinated category (1652-1628 cm⁻¹).

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